

**USE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF LOYALTY PROGRAMMES IN HOTELS IN
SAUDI ARABIA**

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2019

Abstract

The aim of this study is to investigate the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia. Millions of tourists visit and stay in hotels in Saudi Arabia. However, there is a lack of research addressing the use of loyalty programs in the country. A review of the literature on loyalty programmes revealed a gap in knowledge on the extent to which loyalty programmes affect customer loyalty, specifically in Saudi Arabia's hotel industry. The study employed a qualitative approach to data collection by using semi-structured interviews with 11 hotel managers in Saudi Arabia and a thematic analysis of their responses. The results indicate that loyalty programmes have special benefits for most hotels using them, including an increase in revenue, profit generation, customer retention and attraction. The results also show that hotels in Saudi Arabia utilise a number of ways to measure the effectiveness of loyalty programmes, such as participation and redemption rates along with return on investment. Furthermore, this study found that hotels in Saudi Arabia have all developed special policies to protect the customer data gathered by their loyalty programmes. The findings from this study suggest that hotels that do not use loyalty programmes are missing a very beneficial relationship marketing tool and should, thus, be encouraged to adopt it. As a recommendation for further research, it is suggested that more studies be carried out on the impact of customer satisfaction on the success of loyalty programmes.

Acknowledgment

I would like to thank my supervisor of the research Dr. Rodrigo Lucena De Mello for all help and support in this study. The support and feedback I received that have guided me to improve my understanding and performance in order to be able to submit my final project. he provided not only academic help through this academic year but also he gave me all the moral support and constant encouragement for any issues I have encountered to achieve my academic goal.

I want to thank the Saudi government who have helped me and provide all support and guide me to achieve all my goals and offered financial support this year.

Furthermore, I want to thank the study participants. They spent their time to give me their opinions and insights that have presented to the findings of this final project.

Also, I have a list of individuals that have helped me through this academic year. Firstly, I would like to acknowledge the most important persons in life. my mother and my father, they have offered the pastoral support not just at this year but all my life. secondly, I want to thank my wife for her support for me, despite all the difficulties we faced during my studies and when she was pregnant, labour day and taking care of my son. Finally, I would like to thank my grandparents to help me to be a successful person and everything they made for me. I will be grateful to you all!

I confirm that this project is my own work and no part of it has been previously published elsewhere or submitted as part of any other module assessment.

Word Count: 13,733

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

The biggest challenge that current businesses are facing involves retaining their customers while increasing customer loyalty due to intense competition in the modern market (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). Customer attraction comes with major marketing costs, which also requires more efforts to make the customer loyal to the company (Nastasoiu and Vandebosch, 2019). In the face of modern competition, the tourism and hospitality sectors have adopted the loyalty reward system as a relationship-marketing tool making resulting in their proliferation as companies seek for competitive advantage by increasing customer loyalty (Dekay, Toh, and Raven, 2009). The key factor driving this marketing trend is that companies cannot afford to lose any of their customers in the current competitive environment.

Therefore, since their introduction in American Airlines, the loyalty programmes have been adopted by various industries across the world (Dekay, Toh, and Raven, 2009). Competition in the hospitality industry is heightened by customers having access to multiple sources of information when selecting among hospitality choices, which leads to many companies having trouble in increasing their market share (Nastasoiu and Vandebosch, 2019). Thus, businesses have shifted from being product- to customer-centric as they adopt different customer-relationship management tools (Kong and Liang, 2012).

Enhancing customer loyalty reduces acquisition costs while increasing revenue (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). Several studies have emphasised on the significance of repeat patronage of customers as purchase amount increases with the

increase in the number of visits (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). In addition, repeat customers bring with them new customers through the positive word of mouth (Sharp and Sharp, 2011). The key aim of loyalty programmes is to increase profit, revenue, and market portion by growing customer loyalty (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). Most service organisations in the hospitality sector consider relationship strategies as a means of attracting, maintaining, and enhancing customer relationships while obtaining long-term competitiveness (Nastasoiu and Vandenbosch, 2019). The hospitality sector has realised that searching for new customers is not enough in the modern market (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). The results have been a shift to increasing customer loyalty such that loyalty marketing has become an ideal and necessary move to increase competitive advantage (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). A study by Accenture, the well-known global consultancy company, found that members of loyalty programmes contribute 12 to 18% annual increments in revenue growth in companies (Wollan et al., 2017). For instance, in the US, 57% of consumers spend more on brands to which they are loyal indicating that loyalty programmes were a beneficial investment (Wollan et al., 2017). Loyalty programmes can also be used in identifying potential markets while gathering information about customers (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017).

One major aspect of customer loyalty involves data collection that is later used in tailoring the marketing tool as a form of target marketing (Baumann, Elliott and Burton, 2012). Loyalty programmes provide a suitable destination for data mining as they allow businesses to track customer purchasing behaviour in a detailed manner (Kong and Liang, 2012). Thus, organisations consider this type of tracking as a profitable approach for getting data for analysis. Furthermore, due to increase in data security, organisations

employ computerised tracking methods in protecting themselves from losses associated with fraud (Al-Saggaf and Islam, 2014). Some of the key information that can be collected includes customer location, product or service purchased, price paid, and time of purchase. All this information can be used when tailoring loyalty programmes to align with customer needs (Kong and Liang, 2012). Most businesses collect customer data by following the products and services purchased by the loyalty programme members, which can be used in product planning (Baumann, Elliott, and Burton, 2012).

Loyalty programmes could be particularly significant for the hotel industry in Saudi Arabia. The Saudi economy is heavily reliant on oil and gas. Thus, the government's vision is to diversify the economy, and, among other things, make tourism a booming sector (Al-Saud, 2016). Saudi Arabia is not a popular tourist destination, particularly when compared to the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Nonetheless, data from the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) shows that, in 2017, the contribution of tourism to Saudi GDP was \$64.2 billion. In addition, the sector supported 1, 1116, 500 jobs directly and indirectly, and is expected to continue growing in the coming years (Turner, 2018). For hotels in Saudi Arabia, building the confidence of consumers through loyalty programmes may be crucial to the continuous growth of their business through competitive advantage. However, despite the rapid growth and use of loyalty programmes, many questions have arisen regarding their effectiveness in influencing customer loyalty.

Therefore, this study may provide the hospitality industry in Saudi Arabia with key information about the effectiveness and long-run impact of such programmes. The current study also attempts to understand the long-term effect of loyalty programmes on customer loyalty. The results from the study may, thus, provide valuable insight for

Saudi Arabia hospitality marketers (and, arguably, from other regions of the world), who may develop strategies for measuring the effectiveness of loyalty programmes in the long-term. Importantly, in doing so, the current study also serves to add information to the body of literature on the use of loyalty programmes, particularly in contexts experiencing a growth in the hospitality industry.

1.2 Research Aim and Objectives

In view of the remarks above, the aim of the current study is to investigate the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia. To achieve this aim, the following research objectives were identified:

1. To critically review the literature on customer loyalty and loyalty programmes with a focus on the hospitality industry (Secondary).
2. To investigate the extent to which hotels in Saudi Arabia use loyalty programs (Primary).
3. To investigate whether the use of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia has an impact on attracting new customers (Primary).
4. To investigate whether the use of loyalty programmes has helped hotels in Saudi Arabia increase business through customer retention (Primary).
5. To determine how hotels in Saudi Arabia manage the data they collect from customers via loyalty programmes. (Primary)
6. To draw a conclusion on the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia (Primary and Secondary).

1.3 Brief explanation of Data collection

To achieve the aim and objectives above mentioned, this study employed a qualitative approach to data collection with the use of qualitative semi-structured interviews carried out with hotel managers in Saudi Arabia. The information collected focuses on the way loyalty programmes are used to enhance their relationship with customers and how these hotel managers measure the effectiveness of their programmes.

1.4 Outline of the Dissertation

This dissertation has five chapters. Chapter one introduces the topic and highlights the background of these topics, outlines the aim and objectives of this study and discusses the rationale of this study.

Chapter two focuses on the literature review that outlines the various studies that have been carried out in the field of marketing and use of loyalty programmes. It discusses the types of loyalty and loyalty programmes utilised by different organisations to enhance customer loyalty. More importantly, this chapter critically discusses the links between loyalty and customer satisfaction while thoroughly analysing and evaluating the metrics for measuring the effectiveness of loyalty programmes. Finally, the chapter winds up by highlighting the gap in research that leads to the need for the current study to be carried out.

Chapter three focuses on the methodology and methods used in this study. It highlights the various approaches to data collection and analysis while explaining the use of interpretivism as a research philosophy in this study. This chapter also elaborates on the sampling technique used, fully explains and justifies the use of semi-structured interviews as data collection methods while detailing the thematic data analysis

technique employed. The chapter concludes with ethical considerations and the measures taken, for example, to protect research participants and data confidentiality. Chapter four covers the findings obtained from the data collected. The thematic analysis used led to the emergence of six themes, namely, current loyalty programmes, benefits of loyalty programmes, measurement of the effectiveness of loyalty programmes, information used when building loyalty programmes, improving customer attraction and retention, and data collection and privacy. These themes are then discussed in-depth and participants' quotes are used to underpin the arguments put forward in the chapter. Chapter five concludes by clearly stating how each of the research objectives were achieved. It also provides recommendations to the hospitality industry and makes suggestions for further research based on this study's findings.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews the literature on the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia. As such, it is divided into eight sections. The first discusses customer loyalty in general, incorporating types of loyalty and the link between this and customer satisfaction. The second discusses loyalty programmes and the types of loyalty programmes that exist; this section also outlines the metrics for measuring the effectiveness of loyalty programmes and data mining. The next section deals with customer loyalty in the hospitality sector and looks at the challenges faced by hospitality loyalty programmes. The final section introduces the research gap that this study intends to fill.

2.2 Customer Loyalty

Bijmolt, Dorotic and Verhoef (2010) defines customer loyalty as the act of a customer consistently preferring one company's products and services to their competitors'. It is difficult to convince a loyal customer to choose a substitute product or service from another company over the one they are used to even if the other company's prices are competitive (Tixier, 2011). Loyalty is generally achieved when a business consistently meets and surpasses customers' expectations (Nastasoiu and Vandebosch, 2019). There is a good chance that consumers who trust the business they engage with will be more likely to acquire services or products from them in the future (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014). These definitions are key to this study that evaluates the effectiveness of loyalty programmes.

According to Kim and Ahn (2017), customer loyalty is an essential aspect that every business or company strives to achieve. This is because it is easier to keep loyal customers than to get new ones (Nafei, 2014). A business cannot survive if customers do not continuously purchase products or services. Repeat customers are what all businesses envision when they start the company (Kang, Alejandro, and Groza, 2015). Customers represent the main pillars of growth and profits (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). There are also subtle benefits when customers come back consistently to buy from a company because they act as a marketing tool, referring the company to other customers via word of mouth (Seh Tah and Darko, 2018).

Goldsmith and Salehuddin Mohd Zahari (2014) compare a successful business to a bucket with customers acting as the water filling it up. Less successful businesses can be compared to a bucket with a hole: even if the customers continue to flow in, they will never fill the bucket because water will leak through the hole. Goldsmith and Salehuddin Mohd Zahari (2014) use this metaphor to make the point that even if a company has loyal customers, it is essential to practice good customer retention strategies. Kong and Liang (2012) also argue that a business needs to make an effort to foster customer loyalty to ensure sustainability. As such, the only way to keep a firm's customers is through product differentiation and product quality improvement (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014).

Yi and Jeon (2013) suggest three established conceptualisations of customer loyalty. The first model sees customer loyalty as an attitude towards a brand (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014). For loyalty commitment towards a brand to develop, the customer should have a strong attitude towards it (see Figure 1). According to the second model (also illustrated in Figure 1), loyalty is primarily defined in terms of the behaviour

displayed by the customer so that habit and satisfaction define their loyalty to a given brand. This model is, however, controversial because it fails to consider the commitment or the motivation of the customer to engage in such behaviour (Tixier, 2011).

The third model defines loyalty in terms of the customer's individual characteristics (including preferences and needs) and purchase circumstances (including purchasing power) (Tixier, 2011).

Figure 1: Conceptualisations of customer loyalty (Tixier, 2011)

Studies on customer loyalty focus on its various aspects, such as the factors that influence loyalty and types of customer loyalty, such as customer behaviour and customer attitude. Customer loyalty can be triggered by an individual's rational and emotional factors related to the way they perceive a product in terms of quality and its

ability to meet their needs (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). Retaining customers is considered to be the main challenge faced by businesses today and in the future. Therefore, if companies are to ensure retention they have to satisfy their consumers as unsatisfied consumers tend to switch brands.

To try to gain customer loyalty, companies often initiate programmes to enable customers to express their satisfaction or to make complaints (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014). A firm can measure their customers' loyalty based on the intention to repurchase, the recommendation of the product to other customers, and the extent to which they agree with pricing (Dekay, Toh, and Raven, 2009). Based on this feedback, companies can and should make significant changes to product features if they are to ensure their customers' loyalty (Nastasoiu and Vandenbosch, 2019).

Research shows that there exists a relationship between profitability, customer loyalty and customer satisfaction (Stathopoulou and Balabanis, 2016). Customer satisfaction refers to the overall evaluation by the client of their experience of purchasing and consuming a given product (Baumann, Elliott, and Burton, 2012). Loyalty relates to the intention to repurchase from a company (Baumann, Elliott, and Burton, 2012). Therefore, a satisfied customer becomes loyal to a firm, and a loyal customer will help a business to profit (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). Firms can find it difficult to make consumers loyal to their products (Baumann, Elliott, and Burton, 2012). Customer satisfaction relates to the emotional situation that results when the feeling surrounding disconfirmed expectations is linked with previous emotions regarding a given product (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014).

2.2.1 Types of Loyalty

The three types of loyalty that are discussed in this section are emotional loyalty, attitudinal loyalty and behavioural loyalty.

Emotional loyalty towards a product or brand usually develops based on factors like customer service, trust, storytelling or philanthropy (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). Customers who have high emotional engagement are usually more likely to develop strong brand affinity in comparison to customers with low emotional engagement (Nastasoiu and Vandenbosch, 2019).

Attitudinal loyalty can occur when a customer tells potential consumers about the benefits of a product or when someone just feels positive about the brand (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). Customers with attitudinal loyalty are important for any business as they add strength to the brand (Kang, Alejandro, and Groza, 2015). Additionally, word of mouth by attitudinally loyal customers is also central to the brand as it is a key means of free promotion (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000). Attitudinal loyalty develops when a customer chooses to be loyal because of their positive preference, as they believe the brand can fulfil their functional and emotional needs (Nastasoiu and Vandenbosch, 2019).

Behavioural loyalty develops when a customer consistently buys a given product for reasons including positive preference in the form of attitudinal loyalty, but this can also be due to apathy and captive loyalty (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000).

This analysis of the different types of customer loyalty indicates that customer satisfaction can be perceived in different ways leading to faithfulness to a specific brand (Baumann, Elliott, and Burton, 2012).

2.2.2 The Link between Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction

For loyalty to develop, customer satisfaction is vital (Szczepańska and Gawron, 2011). If a product meets the customer's expectations, loyalty may develop. Customer satisfaction is key to any firm seeking to maintain its competitive advantage (Vorina and Veljkovic, 2012). In terms of hotels, these being the focus of this study, research has found that many guests are attracted to a hotel's external image. There is also a direct relationship between housekeeping and customer loyalty (Seh Tah and Darko, 2018). According to Vorina and Veljkovic (2012), customers record high satisfaction scores when they check into clean and well-furnished rooms. After finding that guests' low satisfaction scores led to a significant decrease in the number of customer returns, Seh Tah and Darko (2018) recommended that hotel managers ensure that their guests receive the best possible service to sustain customer loyalty so that they can remain competitive in the industry. To achieve the optimum level of customer loyalty, customers can be included in various loyalty programmes (Nastasoiu and Vandebosch, 2019). These programmes are the focus of the next section.

2.3 Loyalty Programmes

According to Dorotic, Bijmolt, and Verhoef (2011), the first loyalty schemes were created in the 19th century. They were introduced as a means of retaining customers when firms started to lose their competitive advantage (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). According to Stathopoulou and Balabanis (2016), 90% of customers participate in one or more types of loyalty programme. Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner (2017) found that 95% of Canadians and 92% of the UK population participate in two or more loyalty programmes.

Loyalty programmes are marketing tools that work through awarding the customer rewards such as gifts, discounts or bonuses. Their aim is to motivate customers to make multiple and frequent purchases of services or goods and to make them loyal (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). To achieve customer loyalty, it is crucial to meet and surpass customers' expectations to convert them to loyal customers, thus generating more revenue (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014). When incorporating loyalty programmes into a business, a firm should be flexible in what they offer in order to get as many customers as possible (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014). In addition, according to Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner (2017), by consistently providing loyalty programmes to customers, they will start visiting the business regularly. However, to achieve customer loyalty, it is crucial to meet and surpass the expectations of the customers to convert them to loyal customers, thus, generating more revenue (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014).

According to Szczepańska and Gawron (2011), a loyalty programme's purpose should be to achieve two things. Firstly, it should increase the products or services bought, which in turn increases the firm's revenue. Secondly, the customers should be retained by fostering a close working relationship between them and the firm's staff (Vorina and Veljkovic, 2012). When this is achieved, the firm's profit margin may significantly increase.

2.3.1 Types of Loyalty Programme

According to Seh Tah and Darko (2018), there are two types of loyalty programme. Type one, reward loyalty, occurs when customers show a loyalty card at the point of sale to get a discount on a product (Dorotic, Bijmolt, and Verhoef, 2011). This type of programme is characterised by open membership, with every customer having the

chance to receive the same discount without their previous buying history being taken into consideration. The key benefit of this type of loyalty programme is how easy it is to run as customers do not need to sign up for it (NastasoIU and Vandebosch, 2019). However, the lack of tailoring to individual customers means that it does not necessarily create loyalty (Seh Tah and Darko, 2018).

The second type of loyalty programme is the membership card. When a customer signs up for a card, they get points when they make payments that they can use for future discounts or other rewards. These enable firms to track their customers' buying habits (Bijmolt, Dorotic and Verhoef, 2010). The key advantage of this programme is that it makes it easy for the firm to track their customer base, including frequency of purchases and visits (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). However, this programme has one major disadvantage, which is customers' protection. As it involves the use of customers' personal information like phone number, full name and email address their privacy is at risk (Stathopoulou and Balabanis, 2016).

Other shortcomings related to the use of loyalty programmes are the cost of implementing the programmes and bias concerns (Kong and Liang, 2012). Firms have to be selective when choosing those to reward, which are normally those who will make the most purchases.

2.3.2 Metrics for Measuring the Effectiveness of Loyalty Programmes

Those working in hotel management should be aware of the importance of measuring the effectiveness of loyalty programmes (Deepa and Chitramani, 2014). Implementing a loyalty programme does not necessarily mean it will benefit a hotel's operation processes unless this is done well (Uncles, Dowling and Hammond, 2003). Client

loyalty should be measured in terms of the lifetime value that can be obtained from the loyalty programmes (Sharp and Sharp, 2011). The cost of product development and expenses used to support the client should be negated (Yi and Jeon, 2003). This makes it easy to understand suitable discount and retention rates, and overall costs. However, the success of a loyalty programme ought not to be entirely based on financial matters but should reflect the other activities that help to support it (Tunsi, 2010). Mohsin, Ramli, and Alkhulayfi (2016) analysed the success of a loyalty programme based on acquisition costs, client retention and rate of purchases. Understanding client satisfaction levels is essential in a hotel achieving greater financial success (Jehanzeb et al., 2013).

Measuring the effectiveness of a loyalty programme can be challenging when financial measures are undertaken, a conclusion can be developed based on the available loyalty programmes. (Sharp and Sharp, 2011). Data collection is a major issue since loyalty programmes target many customers (Doole, Blackmore, and Schilizzi, 2014). It is also difficult to quantify non-tangible factors such as consumer feelings and attitudes (Mohsin, Ramli, and Alkhulayfi, 2016). Too much information is often collected that is unnecessary (Goodman, 2011). In other cases, it is challenging to collect accurate data about a customer especially as people have become more worried about their privacy in recent times. Loyalty programmes therefore need to make a huge effort to protect personal data (Tunsi, 2010). If the business fails to implement appropriate security measures to protect customer data then they will face reduced loyalty from customers (Mohsin, Ramli, and Alkhulayfi, 2016). Thus, data such as credit card numbers and passport information should be kept safely (Mohsin, Ramli, and Alkhulayfi, 2016).

In the current competitive business environment, almost all businesses have adopted loyalty programmes as marketing tools (Kang, Alejandro, and Groza, 2015).

This ubiquity is a challenge because companies often now merely copy whatever their competitors are offering (Dekay, Toh, and Raven, 2009). It is also essential to understand that interpreting the effects of sales based on a loyalty programme can be a difficult undertaking and this makes it harder to understand the cause of profitability in the organisation (Sharp and Sharp, 2011).

2.3.3 Data Mining in Loyalty Programmes

According to Goodman (2011), data mining is critical in loyalty programmes because it enables businesses to track and define the buying behaviour of their customers. Most large businesses around the world use this kind of tracking to acquire data for analysis (Kong and Liang, 2012). The customer data that businesses can collect through loyalty programmes includes names, genders, dates of birth, email addresses, postal or zip addresses (Al-Saggaf and Islam, 2014). This data is essential in building databases of customer information, which the company will use to send targeted promotional messages (Kong and Liang, 2012) as well as to have a good understanding of their customers so they know who to market to in the future.

Some businesses have developed applications (apps) specifically for smartphones to facilitate customers to get coupons and identify themselves without needing to walk around with membership cards (Kang, Alejandro, and Groza, 2015). Customers can use smartphone apps created by hotels to set up accounts and make bookings or reservations (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). Al-Saggaf and Islam (2014) mention that smartphones provide very crucial data for hotels that could otherwise be unavailable via other traditional loyalty programmes. This provides

information that is crucial to tracking customers, such as their email address (Kong and Liang, 2012).

However, data mining does present several challenges (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). This includes poor quality data, such as incorrect or missing values, and inadequate representation in a data sample. Moreover, integrating redundant or conflicting data from diverse sources is difficult (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner, 2017). Some data is difficult to access or is unavailable (Goodman, 2011). Of all the potential challenges, ethical issues, such as privacy, have the most impact (Goodman, 2011). For example, it is unethical to use mined data for a different function other than the one specified or assumed (Tixier, 2011): such as to sell customers' information to third-party companies when they believe their information is being kept for the company's records (Goodman, 2011). Data privacy and security underwent rigorous change with the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) legislation passed by the European Union in May 2018, holding companies more accountable for the misuse of customers' data, putting another level of pressure on companies' data mining activities (Goodman, 2011).

2.4 Customer Loyalty in the Hospitality Sector

The phenomenon of rewarding customers for their loyalty is common in most sectors, including hotels (Dekay, Toh, and Raven, 2009). The international hotel sector has, for many years, participated in different marketing strategies using relationship management to build long-term relationships with customers (Nastasoiu and Vandenbosch, 2019). In the face of growing competition, hotels tend to employ loyalty programmes as their key relationship management tool (Dekay, Toh, and Raven, 2009). Loyalty programmes' popularity with consumers has resulted in their proliferation across the industry, with

firms using this strategy as a means of gaining a competitive advantage (Nastasoiu and Vandenbosch, 2019).

Some researchers feel that having 100% loyalty to a firm such as a hotel is not easy given that customers, especially in this sector, usually have polygamous loyalty (Dorotic, Bijmolt, and Verhoef, 2011). Polygamous loyalty is when a customer demonstrates loyalty towards different brands at the same time, sometimes simply for a desire for variety (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003). Polygamous loyalty tends to have a serious effect as it transforms the concept of loyalty programmes from a positive into a defensive one where it is used to try to retain customers instead of stimulating their loyalty (Kang, Alejandro, and Groza, 2015).

Therefore, even with the significance of loyalty programmes, it is unjustified to expect guests to be loyal to one brand without the possibility of using other alternatives in the market (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003). Consequently, while loyalty programmes are widely used in the hospitality sector, it is difficult to define their effectiveness due to the presence of polygamous loyalty and customers' difficulties in understanding loyalty programmes (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003). Furthermore, the fact that almost every company in the hospitality sector has adopted a different type of loyalty programme makes it difficult for customers to differentiate between these.

2.4.1 Loyalty Programmes in the Hospitality Sector

There are four types of loyalty programmes in the hospitality sector (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003). Type II loyalty programmes are often used in the food and beverage (F&B) sector, focusing on quality discount while the customer manages the

programme (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003). Type II loyalty programmes are considered the least expensive and easy to manage but offer a poor understanding of the customer. Type III loyalty programmes are usually offered in the hotel and airline sectors; they involve the tracking of information regarding a number of points that are used later when rewarding clients (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003). This type of programme usually benefits the company as it often leads to a better understanding of the consumer while generating a high sense of loyalty among customers (Nastasoiu and Vandenbosch, 2019). However, the benefits of this type of programme must be offset against the costs accrued in the management of the database and the data collection.

Type IV loyalty programmes divide customers into groups based on the frequency of their purchases. When using this type of programme, there is a need for a comprehensive database that offers important demographic information regarding purchase histories and patterns (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003). Type IV loyalty programmes are usually cost-effective as the rewards, such as coupons, are normally distributed to targeted customers (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003).

Additionally, hybrid programmes combine these four types of loyalty programmes (Uncles, Dowling, and Hammond, 2003). However, without careful strategic planning, the companies using these programmes in combination can lose or overlap their objectives (Palmer, McMahon-Beattie, and Beggs, 2000).

In the hotel sector, the Type II loyalty programme offers a suitable means of tracking customer purchases while developing efficient reward systems and is thus frequently used.

2.4.2 Challenges Faced by Hospitality Loyalty Programmes

The major challenge that hospitality loyalty programmes face relates to competitive advantage. Marketing offers hospitality companies the primary means of gaining a competitive advantage. However, the most successful loyalty programmes provide a short-lived competitive advantage as they are easily replicated by companies (Stathopoulou and Balabanis, 2016). Furthermore, loyalty programmes are a short-run solution to a long-run product or service differentiation challenges in the increasingly commoditised hospitality sector. The airline sector only redeems on average 11% of miles earned while recording a large volume of unredeemed miles (Stathopoulou and Balabanis, 2016). Thus, low redemption rates make loyalty programmes profitable but the limits in their flexibility affect the value created for the company and may not enable them to maintain or gain a competitive advantage.

Another major challenge when using loyalty programmes is reciprocity. Value generation from loyalty programmes is based on the reciprocal action theory, where the action interpreted by a single side in exchange for a relationship is reciprocated in kind by the other side (Tunsi, 2010). Based on the behavioural commitment theory, the exchange between a client and a product provider does not equate to the interpersonal relationship that is needed for holding the reciprocal action theory. Loyalty, behaviour and attitude are sociological constructs, which cannot be easily applied to low-risk buying (Sharp and Sharp, 2011). The traditional view of hospitality loyalty programmes is that they do not involve any previous commitment by client, which implies that customers will expect more services and amenities for a low cost without giving the hospitality provider anything in return except money.

2.5 Research Gap

The hotels in Saudi Arabia are receiving many visitors every year. According to Vorina and Veljkovic (2012), more than 14 million tourists visit Saudi Arabia every year and the majority of them stay in hotels. Therefore, Saudi Arabia is a relevant context for this type of study. This research is an endeavour to find out to what extent loyalty programmes affect customers' loyalty to hotels in Saudi Arabia. The need for the research is justified by the number of tourists arriving and the number of hotels opening in the country (El-Garaihy, 2013). As a result, this research will seek to find out to what extent loyalty programmes affect customer loyalty to hotels in Saudi Arabia. The country provides a suitable environment to research the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels. This study examines the factors that lead to customer loyalty and how customers evaluate the products and services that they receive as well as the use and effectiveness of customer loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia (Kim and Ahn, 2017). Little research has been done on this topic in the country despite the tremendous financial benefits associated with customer loyalty (Mohsin, Ramli, and Alkhulayfi, 2016). This study is an attempt to bridge the gap.

The next chapter details the methodology used to achieve the study's aim and objectives.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents and justifies the methods used in this research on the use of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia. It explains the way this study was conducted by focusing on factors such as research philosophy, research strategy and the instruments used to collect the data and achieve the objectives. Other key sections in this chapter include sample selection, research design, research approach, method of data analysis employed, and ethical considerations when carrying out the research.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy relates to beliefs regarding the way data is gathered, analysed, and employed in developing a conclusion around the set research questions (Caldas, 2003). The epistemology, which describes what is known to be true, and the doxology, which relates to what is believed to be true, are essential aspects of different research philosophies (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2016).

The two main research philosophies adopted in the Western tradition of science are interpretivism and positivism (Crossan, 2003). Interpretivism assumes that reality can only be properly understood through its subjective interpretation (Kratochwill, 2015). Thus, the key element of interpretivism involves investigating the phenomenon in its natural setting while realising that the human aspect cannot be prevented from influencing it (Crossan, 2003). According to Creswell and Creswell (2017), the positivist research philosophy assumes reality to be stable and states that it can be observed or described using an objective viewpoint without the researcher having to interfere with the phenomena under study.

The positivist approach assumes that society shapes an individual in the sense that it considers the social facts that control people (Crossan, 2003). Consequently, within the positivist approach, individual behaviour is dependent on norms expressed through socialisation (Kratochwill, 2015). However, the interpretivist approach assumes that people have consciousness and are intricate and complex, so there are variations in the way they perceive and understand the same objective reality (Crossan, 2003). Another major characteristic of positivism is that it aims at uncovering the laws governing human behaviour and prefers quantitative methods that provide an opportunity for the researcher to be detached from the respondents (Kratochwill, 2015). In interpretivism, the point of research entails gaining an in-depth insight into the lives of the respondents and gaining an empathetic understanding of their way of life (Crossan, 2003). In this sense, qualitative methods are interpretivists' preferred research approach (Caldas, 2003).

This study employed interpretivism as a research philosophy, seeking to interpret social elements related to the effectiveness of loyalty programmes. This was because the focus was on the acquisition of a deep insight from hotel managers into the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes used by their companies.

3.3 Research Design

Research design relates to the way one plans a research project, logically integrating various components to address the research problem holistically (Gill, Stewart, Treasure, and Chadwick, 2008). Thus, the research design is usually determined by the research problem under study. As the researcher aimed to study the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia, the exploratory research design was

employed to gain an insight into, and a familiarity with the problem at hand. The exploratory research design helped the researcher to understand the best way to proceed when studying the issue of loyalty programmes and it was, therefore, considered suitable to use the qualitative research approach. The rationale of using an exploratory design was to gain familiarity with the basic details in order to acquire a well-grounded picture of the use of loyalty programmes in hotels (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2016).

3.3.1 Comparison of Qualitative and Quantitative Research

The research design also relates to the methods used during the research project, with two sorts traditionally dominating research: quantitative and qualitative. The basic difference between qualitative and quantitative research is in the analytic objectives, the sort of questions asked, the sort of data collection instrument and the forms of data produced (Mayer, 2015). For instance, qualitative methods are normally text-based while quantitative methods tend to be number-based. Furthermore, qualitative research does not use statistical tests while quantitative methods do (Creswell, 2009).

Quantitative methods involve collecting data in a numeric form before putting this into categories for developing graphs from raw data (Caldas, 2003). The aim of this mode of research is to establish general laws of the phenomena in question across different settings and/or to serve as a test for a given theory (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015). Different methods can be used to obtain quantitative data, including experiments and questionnaires (Caldas, 2003). The key feature of the quantitative method is that it seeks to control extraneous variables by conducting lab studies (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015). The aim is to achieve objectivity, which, in line with a positivist philosophy, exists separately to the researcher (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

Quantitative research is usually quick and cost-effective to undertake (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Additionally, quantitative methods enable the researcher to test a given hypothesis, while, as explained earlier, the statistical nature allows for generalisation (Gill, Stewart, Treasure, and Chadwick, 2008). Furthermore, the samples used in the quantitative method are randomised, which ensures the research is anonymous thus protecting the participants' data and ensuring confidentiality (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015). However, the disadvantages of the quantitative method are that it may not allow the researcher to obtain such specific and precise data as they might get if they used qualitative methods (Gill, Stewart, Treasure, and Chadwick, 2008). Another disadvantage is that the method does not allow for follow-up on any answers given by respondents (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Quantitative data is also linked to the inability to give access to rich data, and it can be difficult to build a rapport between the researcher and the respondent (Gill, Stewart, Treasure, and Chadwick, 2008).

The advantages of using the qualitative method are that it is the most effective one for exploratory purposes (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). Qualitative research is a less generalisable approach than quantitative research, in which the researcher uses semi-structured or unstructured questions (Caldas, 2003). Qualitative methods facilitate the acquisition of rich information, which is difficult to obtain via quantitative methods (Gill, Stewart, Treasure, and Chadwick, 2008). Thus it is the one that is most commonly used for research projects. On the other hand, one of the disadvantages of qualitative methods is that the researcher is prone to bias and personal subjectivity (Mayer, 2015).

3.3.2 Justification for the Use of the Qualitative Approach

The need to acquire data in the form of narratives from the participants' point of view presents the need for a researcher to use the qualitative method instead of the quantitative method that presents data in the form of numbers (Bean, 2007). A narrative approach helped the research to gain more personal information thus increasing the amount of information provided in answer to the research questions (Creswell, 2009).

Qualitative research entails studies to be conducted on the phenomenon under investigation in its natural setting (Thornhill, Saunders, and Lewis, 2009). The purpose of employing qualitative research is to aid in understanding the social reality and culture of the participants in relation to the subject of the study, in this case, the use of loyalty programmes (Creswell, 2009). Research that follows the qualitative approach is usually exploratory, which seeks to explain why and how a given phenomenon operates in a particular way in a given context (Mayer, 2015). Thus, for this study, the research participants, hotel managers in Saudi Arabia, were studied in the natural environment of the hotels in which they worked.

Given the close involvement of the researcher in the data collection process, the qualitative method ensured that the researcher gains an insider view of the phenomena and thus find issues that have been missed or unnoticed to date (Caldas, 2003). The method also helps in developing possible relations and dynamic processes (Mayer, 2015). Consequently, the fact that qualitative analysis allows for ambiguity and contradictions in the data is an indication that it offers a reflection of social reality (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015). Therefore, the qualitative approach was suitable for this study as it allowed the researcher to have a personal interaction with the participants while gaining a deep understanding of the phenomena.

In this study on the use of loyalty programmes by Saudi Arabian hotels, qualitative methods were used. These methods proved effective in that they enabled the researcher to obtain a clear and in-depth picture of the effectiveness of loyalty programmes (Creswell and Creswell, 2017). The researcher sought to gain answers to questions related to the managers' experience and perspective, which made it appropriate to use the qualitative research approach. The qualitative method helped the researcher to understand the conditions, experiences and personal perspectives of the hotel managers regarding the effectiveness of loyalty programmes (Caldas, 2003).

The qualitative method suited this research as it allowed the researcher to interact with the respondents, as acquiring information on the effectiveness of loyalty programmes relied on the perceptions, comments, views and opinions of those who were interviewed (Caldas, 2003). The research design also helped to overcome the self-consciousness that could have prevented the respondents' impulsive responses and reactions (Caldas, 2003). The qualitative method was in line with the selected interpretive research philosophy.

3.3.3 Sampling Technique, Sample Size and Participant Recruitment

The target population for this study was hotel managers in Saudi Arabia. The researcher employed a purposeful, or criterion-based, sampling technique in acquiring a group to interview regarding the use of loyalty programmes. According to Palinkas et al. (2013), researchers employing qualitative methods commonly use purposeful sampling methods. The reason for using purposeful sampling in this study was to ensure the researcher only focused on a specific group, which were the hotel managers for hotels that used loyalty programmes. In this study, the researcher used purposeful sampling as it helped identify

and select information-rich participants and cases related to the phenomenon under study (Creswell, 2009).

A purposeful sampling technique was employed where managers were selected based on their responsibilities in relation to the loyalty programmes used by their hotels. In finding the participants, the researcher went personally to specific hotels and requested personal interviews with the managers in charge of loyalty programmes. The researcher agreed with the participants on the best day and time to conduct the interview so that it would not interfere with the manager’s hotel programme.

Once a sampling method is determined, the researcher must focus on identifying the sample size for the research. Data collection and analysis for qualitative research usually occur simultaneously so that the researcher can extensively explore the different questions related to the research topic (Sandelowski, 2015). Thus, for this research, the researcher interviewed 11 hotel managers to get an insight into the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia. Table 1 provides the details of the participants who were interviewed.

Name	Hotel	Job
Mr. Samair Melibary	Dana Ragaab Makkah	Director of Sales
Mr. Ahmed Mamdouh	Hilton Convention Makkah	Executive Sales and Guest Members
Mr. Rakan Al-Mutiab	Salsabil By Warwick Jeddah	Sales Manager
Mr. Ahmed Abdullah	Dar Al Haramain Makkah	General Manager
Mr. A.	Hotel 6 Al Naseem Makkah	Sales Manager
Mr. Tahir Mahmoud	Millennium Makkah	Director of Training and

		Development
Mr. Yahia Mahzari	Le Meridien Jeddah	Assistant Director
Mr. Mohammed Abdulazeem	Makarem Ajjad Makkah	Assistant F&B Manager and Guest Relations Manager
Mr. Mustafa Abaza	Movenpick Makkah	Director of Sales
Mr. M.	Hotel 7 Makkah Palace	Front Office Manager
Mr S.	Hotel 8 Al Riyadh	Sales Manager

Table 1: List of the Participants

3.4 Data Collection Method

There are three major methods of data collection used in qualitative research. These are: focus groups, participant observations and interviews (Brannen and Halcomb, 2009). Interviews serve as a means of collecting data on individual perspectives and experiences with a given phenomenon (Mayer, 2015) while providing space for privacy. Thus, this study employed qualitative structured interviews with hotel managers as a means of getting an insight into their experiences with, and perceptions of loyalty programmes. The purpose of using structured interviews was to ensure that the researcher asked similar questions to all of the participants to compare their responses and achieve a supported conclusion regarding the effectiveness of loyalty programmes. The structured interviews allowed for a degree of consistency but also flexibility.

A number of questions, related to the research objectives and stemming from the literature, were asked as a means of getting a clear picture of the use of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia. The questions can be found in Appendix 1. The interviews were conducted between June and July 2019, with each interview lasting for

between 20 and 30 minutes. The interviews were conducted in Arabic, which was later translated into English by the researcher.

The researcher recorded and transcribed all of the interviews for data analysis and also confirmation and validity purposes. Additionally, the researcher took notes on the managers' responses that were compiled for analysis. An example interview transcript can be found in Appendix 2.

3.5 Data Analysis

The data analysis part of the research employed an inductive approach, which created a clear link between the research objectives and the results of the interviews. Data preparation was an important part of the analysis, as it formed a means of converting the raw data collected from the hotel managers into something readable (Mayer, 2015). The data preparation involved data validation for issues like bias and completeness to ensure that the researcher asked all the necessary questions (Mayer, 2015). Once the data were prepared, the next step involved editing for errors. The last step involved data coding, where values were assigned to responses from the managers to have a clear picture of the data collected and to reach a conclusion regarding the research objectives.

In the data analysis process, the first step involved manual transcribing of the data collected from the hotel managers to convert it into a textual form that could be analysed (Mayer, 2015). Due to the large amount of data collected from the hotel managers, another important step involved organising the data based on the research objectives and questions by using tables that classified different responses into a given group of objectives and questions (Dey, 2003). Data coding was an important step towards ensuring proper analysis of the data, as it helped the researcher obtain meaning

from the data collected. The main method of coding involved descriptive coding techniques where the researcher summarised the data based on the central theme (Dey, 2003). A sample coding approach is shown in Appendix 4. The last step involved developing a conclusion on the data by focusing on the link between the data, and the research questions and objectives (Mayer, 2015).

3.6 Research Ethics

The researcher took steps to ensure that the study adhered to various research ethics, such as the privacy of the participants (Bulmer, 2011). The researcher used data only for the purposes it served, which was an understanding of the use of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia. The researcher obtained written consent from the participants before collecting the information. Furthermore, most of the managers agreed to have their names and the names of their hotels included in the report as a means of increasing the validity of the results. For purposes of information handling and confidentiality, the researcher ensured that the managers agreed to have their interview recorded and their names used in the research by signing a participant consent form (see Appendix 3). In case the participant requested anonymity in terms of their name and their hotel's name, the researcher stated that they would use only a letter and number to demarcate this in the list of participants. The interview complied with the hotel's standard policies and also the code of ethics at the University of Brighton. All data was stored on a protected external disk that could only be accessed by the researcher.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Findings

As previously explained, this study aims to investigate the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in various hotels in Saudi Arabia. Interviews were carried out with hotel managers to gain their opinions and perspectives on the loyalty programmes used in their hotels together with their views on the effects and effectiveness of these programmes. Thematic analysis was used to code the data obtained to identify emerging themes.

The following are the primary data-related research objectives that this study set out to achieve:

- To investigate the extent to which hotels in Saudi Arabia use loyalty programmes.
- To investigate whether the use of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia has an impact on attracting new customers.
- To investigate whether the use of loyalty programmes has helped hotels in Saudi Arabia increase business through customer retention.
- To determine how hotels in Saudi Arabia manage the data they collect from customers via loyalty programmes.
- To draw a conclusion on the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia.

The thematic analysis led to the emergence of six themes. Figure 2 shows these themes and how they were achieved.

CODES

THEMES

Figure 2: Coding Process and Themes Identified

These themes are explained in detail in the following section.

4.2 Current Loyalty Programmes

One of the key objectives of this study was to understand the extent to which loyalty programmes are used in hotels in Saudi Arabia. The best way to establish this from the interview responses seemed to be to focus on the types of loyalty programme that have been used as reported by the hotel managers. The first participant to be interviewed, Mr. Abdullah, said that the Dar Al Haramian Makkah was employing the 'Al-Dar rewards programme' in which companies are rewarded with special rates if they make repeat bookings; he indicated that the hotel recognises this loyalty programme as an essential marketing tool, thus implying that hotels in Saudi Arabia are using this strategy.

Mr. Abdullah: "We use the Al-Dar Rewards program, which is very simple for travel, Hajj and Umrah companies. It depends on continuous visits; the company gets special rates for rooms or discounts on hotel services whenever they increase their number of hotel visits, which encourages companies to work with us periodically. The programme was built on this reason and companies that make the most hotel bookings."

In another interview session, Mr. Mamdouh, from the Hilton Jabil Omar Makkah, said that the hotel uses the 'Hilton honors' programme used by Hilton hotels worldwide.

Mr. Mamdouh: “We are using Honors...Hilton Honors. This programme is created by Hilton hotels worldwide. Hilton now has 16 brands all over the world. All these hotels are using the current programme, including our hotel. It is considered one of the most popular loyalty programmes and is widespread.”

Mr. Mahzari, from Le Meridien Jaddah, confirmed that the hotel uses a programme owned by the Marriott Group, which uses the site called marriot.com where customers can get offers in terms of special prices. Le Meridien Hotel is training employees to use the loyalty programme and to market the programme to the customers that help the hotel to reach the goals of the programme and gain new loyal customers.

Mr. Mahzari: “We encourage reception staff to offer the benefits of the programme to customers who register. That helps us to raise the customer base, and this way we have made more profit for our hotel: that is the target of the programme. The Marriott Group trains our staff on how to use and sell the programme.”

Mr. Mohammed and Mr. S. both reported that the types of loyalty programme used in their hotels were Karam Membership and Wyndham Rewards, respectively.

Mr. Mohammed: “Our Programme is the Karam Membership Programme, the loyalty programme in all Makarim Group hotels in the Kingdom, it has been in operation for several years and has been developing in recent years.”

Mr. S: “We are using Wyndham Rewards as a loyalty program in this hotel and with the more than 9,000 hotels worldwide affiliated to the Wyndham Group. It’s a rewarding programme for the frequent guest, like any other loyalty programme for other competitive hotel chains. The programme started in 2012, and I consider it one of the most generous programmes because it offers multiple benefits such as earning points customers can use for online shopping and it can also be redeemed for free nights. Over the past seven years, the programme has developed several times; the group has provided our regional office with all the support and information needed.”

These responses from the selected hotel managers has shown that loyalty programmes are widely used by the hotels in Saudi Arabia as a suitable tool for marketing purposes and that they contribute to customers’ returning. Most hotels depend on two specific types of loyalty programmes: points and rewards that customer can earn the benefits by using the programme continuously.

The research also sought to define the extent to which loyalty programmes have been used in hotels in Saudi Arabia. As a result of the interviews, the researcher found that some loyalty programmes have been in use for more than seven years. Therefore, they have a history of use among the major hotels in Saudi Arabia.

4.3 Benefits of Loyalty Programmes

This theme relates to the various provisions associated with the implementation of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia as well as the advantages to hotels of adopting them. From the interviews, it is evident that hotels benefit from loyalty

programmes in several ways, such as through profit increase, reduction of commission fees to travel companies and stable occupancy rates. For instance, the hotels save on the fee they pay tourism companies when selling their rooms thus reducing the cost of marketing. As reported by Mr. A, such a reduction in marketing costs can raise the hotel revenue by 35%.

Mr. A: “The programme helped to reduce the commission paid to the tourism companies for marketing, as we sell the rooms ourselves and do not need to depend on booking sites because of client loyalty. The programme raised hotel revenues significantly by 35% in a short period.”

This was corroborated by Mr. M.:

Mr. M: “The most important benefit for the programme is to avoid the commission paid to the tourism companies for marketing and selling the rooms. Thus, the hotel reduced expenses and achieved more revenue through the programme.”

According to the managers, other advantages offered by loyalty programmes relate to the increase in customer visits and a significant rise in profit margins.

Mr. Al-Mutiab: “The hotel has benefited a lot, for example, from the Walaa Plus programme. The revenue was a big payoff equivalent to 30% of the profits. I also consider it a free marketing programme, because the hotel has not spent much

money on it and there has been a great turnout from customers. Whatever the discount, there will be a turnout from the guests because this makes the guest feel that he has benefited and earned more.”

Another key benefit associated with the use of loyalty programmes is the increase in customers and customer turnout, reflected in the occupancy rate. Mr. Mamdouh also mentioned that the increasing number of customers using the programme has contributed to profit generation. Factors such as customer turnout, occupancy rate and profit generation are therefore taken into consideration by Saudi Arabia hotel managers when assessing the effectiveness of their loyalty programmes.

4.4 Measurement of the Effectiveness of Loyalty Programmes

The section explores the various factors used by hotel managers in Saudi Arabia to define and measure the effectiveness of loyalty programmes. A variety of measures are employed and these are thus discussed in this section.

Redemption Rate

Redemption rate refers to the number of people who redeem the rewards offered by the hotels. If many customers redeem the rewards offered by the loyalty programmes, this shows that they are effective. Therefore, a high redemption rate is considered a positive indication that a loyalty programme has been successful. An example is the hotel Al Riyadh, which focuses on the redemption rate as a means of identifying the success of its loyalty programme. The rate of redeeming the rewards from the loyalty programmes is one of the suitable metrics that companies employ to assess their success.

Mr. S reported that his hotel measures the effectiveness of their loyalty programme based on the redemption rate:

Mr. S: “Having a high redemption rate is actually a good sign of the effectiveness of the loyalty programme.”

Participation Rate

The participation rate in a loyalty programme is the number of programme members compared to the total number of customers, with a high percentage implying the success of the programme. For instance, when there are many programme members, then this might imply that the programme is successful as it attracts a great number of clients. As the purpose of loyalty programmes is to motivate customers to book and rebook at a hotel, strengthening their relationship with the hotel, a high participation rate represents the programme’s success to the company. As Mr. M said:

Mr. M: “We measure the effectiveness of the programme monthly by the number of memberships. Whenever there are new guests, there is an efficient and responsive loyalty programme.”

Mr. Abdullah: “We have two ways of measuring the effectiveness of our program. First, through the number of companies that have dealt with us and are registered in the programme.”

The participation rate is considered a suitable tool in defining the effectiveness of loyalty programmes, as it helps the company to determine the number of customers that are using the tool. Therefore, there is a need for customers to participate in the programme

to enable the hotels to determine whether it has been accepted and adopted by the consumers. When the consumers engage with the programme, the hotels consider that the programme has achieved its mission and has been adopted by the target company.

Repeat Customers

Repeat-booking implies that customers are satisfied with the services provided by a given company or hotel. The purpose of developing loyalty programmes is to serve as a marketing tool that increases the number of customers that frequent when offering free services to motivate customers to continue visiting a particular hotel. Therefore, when a high number of customers frequent the hotel this serves as an indicator that a loyalty programme has achieved its mission. Thus, the number of repeat customers is used to determine the effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia.

Mr. Melibary: “We measure the effectiveness of our programme by the guests who return and use their loyalty card.”

Mr. Al-Mutiab: “The effectiveness of our programme can be measured by the revenue from loyal customers and by repeated visits.”

Revenue and Return on Investment

One can measure the effectiveness of loyalty programmes by explaining the return on investment in terms of revenue generated before and after introducing the programme. The concept of return on investment involves analysing the loyalty programme-related costs in contrast to the revenue engendered by the programme. The representatives of the hotels who participated in this study illustrated the way that loyalty programmes

have influenced the amount of revenue generated. Mr. Abdullah and Mr. Mamdouh reported that their hotels measure the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes through the revenue that has been earned through the programme.

Mr. Abdullah: “Second, through the revenue which we have earned through the programme.”

Mr. Mamdouh also reported that the hotel measures the effectiveness of their loyalty programme based on the revenue generated by reporting on the revenue generated while using the programme.

Mr. Mamdouh: “we measure the effectiveness of the programme by reporting everything for the programme of revenue.”

Loyalty programmes always imply a need for investment in order to reward customers. This is generally through the provision of something that is given to the customer at a discounted cost or for free: free nights or a free breakfast. While this may translate into significant costs, the hotel managers reported having recorded a specific level of increase in profit and revenue above the initial levels before the loyalty programmes were employed. Therefore, this particular change in revenue, which is used as a measure of return on investment, can be used to define the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes. Most of the hotel managers stated that the introduction of loyalty programmes had seen a major increase in the amount of revenue generated for the company.

However, it is important to note that, while most hotel managers reported having benefited from the use of loyalty programmes, some indicated having experienced challenges when implementing the programme. For example, some participants reported having recorded no benefits with the adoption of the loyalty schemes, which caused

them to abandon the programme, perceived to have failed in achieving company objectives. As Mr. Mohammed mentioned, the loyalty programme did not achieve its expected goals because it could not attract enough customers. Also, hotel customers come in certain seasons of the year as Ramadan or Al-Hajj That period increases the number of visitors to religious tourism where they perform Islamic rites.

Mr. Melibary: “In addition, the revenue generated by our hotel through the programme was unfortunately limited.”

Mr. Mohammed: “The programme was not lucky and we relied on specific guests and repeat customer visits but not our expected from the programme, also the management will now decide whether it is best to continue or terminate the loyalty programme after a full study of the current situation.”

At Dana Ragaab Makkah, the profit generated by the loyalty programme did not match the company’s expectations, which raised the need for the hotel to restructure its scheme by including more advantages and perks for the customers.

Occupancy Rate

The occupancy rate represents one of the major measures of success among key players in the hotel industry. When the loyalty programme is implemented, the aim is to ensure there are increased visits to the hotel, which can be translated into a high occupancy rate. Therefore, it is apparent from the interviews conducted that occupancy rate plays a vital role in defining the success of loyalty programmes by hotels in Saudi Arabia.

Mr. A and Mr. Mamdouh both indicated that their hotels measured the effectiveness of the programme through occupancy rate.

Mr. Mamdouh: “I want to tell you that 25% of the occupancy rate in the hotel is all members of the Hilton Honors.”

Mr. A: “In the hotel, we measure the effectiveness of the programme by check-in in and occupancy rate. There is a 25% rate of guests or total occupancy rate. If the ratio is higher than that percentage (25%), this means it is good, and if the ratio is lower, there is a problem.”

The hotel sector provides services that rely on customers occupying rooms for sleeping purposes. Therefore, the suitability of a particular service will depend on the demand level, which is defined via the occupancy rate, one of a hotel’s ultimate measurements of success. Thus, the occupancy rate is considered a suitable measure of the effectiveness of loyalty programmes, as reported by the hotel managers interviewed in this study.

4.5 Information used when building loyalty programmes

This theme relates to the type of information that hotels require when building or setting-up loyalty programmes. The success of any programme depends on the proper identification of the factors that align with the interests of the customers. The hotel managers interviewed identified that customer needs and preferences form part of the essential information required to develop loyalty programmes. Hotels collect information on the needs of customers when setting-up loyalty programmes as these are

required to act as marketing tools to help attract customers. This is encapsulated in Mr. Mohamed's statement: "We need basic information and to know customer needs to set the goals of the programme."

Managers seek to identify the needs of the customer in order to provide them in the programme; this helps the hotel in achieving the goals of the programme. One major aspect of customer needs and preferences is getting more services at a lower cost. For example, some customers will book one hotel over another if there is even a small reduction in the price of the room rate of the former and simple services in the hotel such as free internet, a free laundry service and a free breakfast are also very welcome. This helps in gaining returning and loyal customers.

Mr. Melibary reported that his hotel focuses on customers' saving-related needs when gathering information for its loyalty programme.

Mr. Melibary: "We needed to provide a new way to attract customers by providing a free night with frequent visits and we try to reach the customer's need to save and get everything."

Mr. Mahzari also indicated that they focus on customers' basic needs and desires when building the loyalty programme. For instance, the hotel looked at key things that each customer would prefer such as free internet.

Mr. Mahzari: "when I will build a loyalty programme, I see what I will offer to the customer and what are the basic things that the customer needs and wants. For example, the Internet is like water for many customers, so I offer free internet to the members and this motivates them to use our Marriot Bonvoy (loyalty programme) and contributes to the success of the programme.

Communication data also helps in setting goals. The company in the latter consider the interest of the client and the company interest.”

4.6 Improving Customer Attraction and Retention

As has been discussed, hotels run loyalty programmes to increase the number of customers that remain loyal to them. Therefore, the various responses provided by the participants in this research proved that loyalty programmes used in hotels in Saudi Arabia do impact customer attraction and retention which serves as a marketing tool to employed to serve as a means of increasing the number of customers using a particular service or product. Mr. Abdullah and Mr. Tahir reported that the loyalty programmes their hotels were using had a great impact and effectiveness in retaining and attracting new customers, which was reflected in the percentage of occupancy.

Mr. Abdullah: “The loyalty programme has a great impact and effectiveness in retaining and attracting customers by companies and this is reflected in our occupancy rate and the number of frequency of client visits in the last few years. These guests are foreign groups which are important to boost the Saudi gross domestic product (GDP).”

From the interviews conducted, it is clear that all the hotels focused on defining the impact of loyalty programmes on customer retention and attraction. Mr. Mamdouh, for example, reported that the loyalty programme that his hotel used had been highly effective in enabling them to retain and attract customers. According to him, the hotel

was attracting new customers who realised the benefits associated with registering as members of the programme.

Mr. Mamdouh: “The programme has a great impact and effectiveness in retaining and attracting customers and this is reflected in our report. The programme is also the best because of the possibilities and the presence of hotels everywhere and the rapid spread of the programme in the world. Our team also attracts new customers after explaining the benefits they will receive when registering a membership and encourages the customer to continue using the programme.”

Mr. Tahir stated:

Mr. Tahir: “The programme has been of great benefit in helping us to retain and attract customers. Once the guest enrolls in the programme and gets the benefit, that makes the customer (more likely to) stay loyal to our brand and that helps or encourages to attract more guests and increase the percentage of occupancy from 17% to 24%.”

The element of customer retention dominated the hotel managers’ responses, implying that it is of great importance as far as loyalty programmes are concerned. Therefore, these findings helped the researcher to achieve the research objective of confirming that the use of loyalty programmes is instrumental in improving business through customer acquisition and retention.

4.7 Data Collection and Privacy

This section focuses on a central aspect of loyalty programmes: the data collected when customers register in loyalty programmes and the way this data is protected. In this vein, information such as customers' date of birth and contact details, such as email address, dominate the type of information collected for use in loyalty programmes. Such data is used for marketing purposes and facilitates the allocation of various offers and services to the respective customers.

Mr. Mahmoud: "We collect some personal information such as the date of birth to offer a very special rate for the room. If the guest's birthday comes when staying in the hotel, he may receive a free night. Contact details can also be collected to assist the client or send offers if he wants or accepts it."

Most of the managers, however, highlighted that the use of data for marketing purposes needs customer approval. For example, when explaining that their hotels focus on gathering communication data for marketing purposes, both Mr. Melibary and Mr. Mamdouh noted that such information is only used with the customer's agreement:

Mr. Melibary: "We focus on communication data for marketing offers or to communicate with and help the customer, but the customer must agree before we do that."

Mr. Mamdouh: “We collect communication data for marketing purposes or to communicate with the customer, but the customer must agree to that.”

Data protection is another important part of the theme identified in the analysis. Loyalty programmes collect a great deal of personal information, thereby raising the need for protection. All the hotels follow an established framework to ensure security, privacy, and confidentiality of the information collected.

Mr. Mamdouh: “There are standards that we commit to ensure the confidentiality of information. We protect the programme through a powerful protection programme that helps in saving data and we warn the client to publish or print their data. Data access is only through the Administrator or the person authorised to manage it by Hilton Group. We also guarantee the confidentiality of the information by conducting training for the team working on the programme and perform annual and ongoing maintenance to protect the programme and the client’s data.”

An important aspect of data protection involves access control. It is clear that, according to all the hotel managers who participated in the interviews, only a specific category of authorised personnel is given access to the customer’s personal information collected by the loyalty programme.

Mr. Tahir: “We have standards and data privacy policy and it is available on our website. We do not send [anyone] or share customer data. The corporate office protects

the data through a security programme and saves it in a secure server. Finally, access to the data [is granted] just by the guest or an authorised person in the Millennium Group.”

To summarise, the use of loyalty programmes involves the collection of data particularly for marketing purposes. While hotels may collect various types of personal information from their clients, special measures are taken to ensure these data do not fall in the wrong hands. In this sense, the presence of privacy policies helps hotels to ensure that the data collected remains safe.

4.8 Discussion

The findings discussed in the previous sections have analysed the various factors related to the research objectives. It has been shown that loyalty programmes are a suitable means of increasing customer retention, as their benefits to the customer can engender an increase in the number of return visits. Consequently, metrics have been outlined for determining the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes; these have highlighted factors like occupancy rate, the return on investment and participation rate as some of the key aspects that hotel managers use when determining the level of effectiveness of loyalty programmes together with the way they influence the business.

The key element of customer loyalty is that customers who place their trust in a particular business will tend to use it repeatedly. The literature on this aspect is supported by the interviews, in which most of the hotel managers confirmed that the loyalty programmes influenced customer retention and the number of repeat customers. The statement by Palmer, McMahon-Beattie and Beggs (2000) that customer loyalty is essential for business as customers represent a special pillar of growth and profit is

supported in the interviews in this research: the managers indicated that customer loyalty, generated by loyalty programmes, has resulted in an increased profit.

Seh Tah and Darko (2018) indicate that there are a variety of benefits associated with customers coming back to businesses aside from profits. The statement is supported by this study, which has shown clearly that customer loyalty is related to the attraction of new customers to hotels, which is good for business growth. Dekay, Toh and Raven (2009) indicate that firms usually measure their customer loyalty based on repurchasing intention and recommendation to other customers. This study further endorses the concept that repeat customers and customer attraction are essential measures of the effectiveness of loyalty programmes.

Stathopoulou and Balabanis' (2016) research finds that a relationship exists between profitability and customer loyalty. The same can be said for loyalty programmes, demonstrating that business success is not only measured in terms of revenue generation but is related to factors such as customer loyalty that sees customers frequently use services offered by hotels. In this study, the participants reported having generated significant profits from their use of loyalty programmes. Therefore, the increase in profit can be related to an increase in the number of loyal customers, which can be traced back to the adoption of loyalty programmes.

Consequently, the results from this study contravene the proposition by Yi and Jeon (2003), who claim the need to eliminate expenses used in supporting the client, as expenses like free breakfasts have been used in loyalty programmes that have had a positive impact on revenue generation. The current research has shown that hotels in Saudi Arabia have employed loyalty programmes as a tool for promoting sales by offering services like free breakfasts and free nights. These results are in line with the

findings by Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner (2017) that giving customers gifts, discounts and bonuses is an essential element of loyalty programmes. Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner (2017) also argue that the consistent use of loyalty programmes will ensure that customers regularly visit the business. The current study supports this idea, as the hotel managers in Saudi Arabia who participated in this research who have been using loyalty programmes have seen a high level of customer retention and return visits. This research has also shown that there are two types of programmes used in hotels in Saudi Arabia, focusing on rewards and points, as proposed by She Tah and Darko (2018).

A significant aspect of the literature review that is reflected in the current study is the metrics for measuring the effectiveness of loyalty programmes. This study supports the recommendation made by Mohsin, Ramli and Alkhulayfi (2016) that the success of loyalty programmes should be based on rates of purchase and client retention. For instance, financial measures such as revenue and customer retention were mentioned by the participants, showing that the financial performance of the hotels and numbers of return visits are essential measures of the effectiveness of loyalty programmes.

Doole, Blackmore and Schilizzi (2014) state that data collection represents a significant challenge in loyalty programmes. Most hotels collect communication data when implementing loyalty programmes. Al-Saggaf and Islam (2014) highlight that some of the customer data collected via loyalty programmes includes gender, date of birth and customer address. The current research corroborates this, highlighting that hotels in Saudi Arabia collect communication data such as email addresses and dates of birth through their loyalty programmes. The challenge is to protect this data and to reassure the customer that it will not be misused. The current research found that most

hotels in Saudi Arabia are employing data protection and privacy policies to ensure the safety of the data collected on their customers.

Goodman (2011) found that data mining was a critical aspect of loyalty programmes, as businesses tend to track their customers' buying behaviour. The trend was noticed for hotels in Saudi Arabia, which built and collect various customers' details to tailor their loyalty programmes in ways that match the needs of their customers. For instance, when the hotel sets-up the loyalty programme, the hotel managers are likely to decide that meeting customer needs through the provision of a free internet service is essential in attracting customers to the hotel. Also, the hotels collect contact details when the customer registers for marketing purposes such as sending special offers to customers is likely to make them return.

A key finding of this research relates to the fact that some companies have incurred a loss of revenue through their loyalty programmes, as there was no change in revenue when they were introduced, thus raising the need to abandon this marketing tool. These findings support the work of Kong and Liang (2012), who note that there have been concerns with the costs involved in implementing loyalty programmes.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study is an investigation of the ways in which hotels in Saudi Arabia use, and measure the effectiveness of their loyalty programmes. This aligns with the purpose of determining whether loyalty programmes have a particular influence on attracting and retaining clients. The literature review explored various theories and past research in the field of customer loyalty and revealed a gap in the study on the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes among hotels in Saudi Arabia. Therefore, this study was developed around key objectives.

The first research objective was to provide a critical review of the literature on customer loyalty and loyalty programmes on the hotel industry in Saudi Arabia. Thus, a thorough review of the literature was conducted (in Chapter 2), covering the studies that have been carried out on the use of loyalty programmes. The review revealed a gap in the research on the measurement of the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes being used in hotels in Saudi Arabia.

The second research objective focused on investigating the use of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia. The interviews with hotel managers from Saudi Arabia found that their hotels have adopted loyalty programmes as a marketing approach and discovered the ways in which they have been using their programmes. For instance, Le Meridien Hotel is training the reception staff to use and market the loyalty programme to new customers by offering the benefits of programme that help the hotel to reach the target of the programme and gain new loyal customers. Therefore, the findings helped the researcher to achieve the objective of investigating the extent of use of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia.

The third and fourth objectives focused on investigating the impact of loyalty programmes on the attraction and retention of customers, respectively. Loyalty programmes were found to have a particular influence on customer retention and attraction. For instance, some managers reported an increase in return visits to their hotel, which is both an indication of and a trigger to customer retention. For example, Mr. Abdullah reported that his hotel had managed to attract new customers through their loyalty programme and that was reflected in the frequency of customer visits.

The study also set out to investigate the approaches that hotels in Saudi Arabia use to measure the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes. The results shed light on the approaches employed when measuring the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes. In this sense, a key element is revenue generation: most hotels that use loyalty programmes focus on revenue and profit generation as a suitable measure of the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes. It is important to note that some hotels reported having recorded a loss from using the loyalty programmes, which has eventually led to the termination of the scheme. These findings also corroborate the concept that revenue is a suitable measure of the effectiveness of loyalty programmes. Another suitable approach to measure the effectiveness of a loyalty programme is through the occupancy rate, as reported by Mr. Mamdouh who stated that 25% of the hotel's occupancy rate comprised the members of the Hilton Honors loyalty programme. Other measures found to provide a metric for the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes were participation rates, repeat customer totals and redemption rates. Thus, the responses provided by the managers allowed for the research objective relating to the measurement of the effectiveness of the loyalty programmes in Saudi Arabia to be met.

The final objective of the study was to determine how hotels in Saudi Arabia manage the data they collect from customers through their loyalty programmes. The findings were that different types of data are collected by hotels in Saudi Arabia via loyalty programmes, most notably relating to personal data and contact details. A common issue associated with collecting customer data was privacy and confidentiality. Therefore, the hotels in Saudi Arabia have an approach to protect customer data that involves the use of privacy policies and ensuring that only authorised personnel have access to the data.

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 Recommendations for the Hospitality Industry

The findings from this study show that hotels in Saudi Arabia have made profitable investments in loyalty programmes and benefited by experiencing increased revenue generation. Therefore, other hotels that have not adopted the programme should consider using this tool. The findings from the research also show that hotels in Saudi Arabia are using these programmes to learn more about and consequently meet their customers' needs through the provision of services such as free internet when setting-up loyalty programmes. The study recommends that the hotels that use loyalty programmes make a major platform for customer preferences and needs.

The findings also indicate that the loyalty programmes were, generally, an effective tool in attracting and retaining customers to the hotels. Therefore, there is a need for hotels to tailor their loyalty programmes by increasing the benefits associated with their use.

5.2.2 Recommendations for Future Research

Further research should be conducted on how customer satisfaction relates to the success or failure of loyalty programmes. More qualitative research could be carried out from the customer's point of view to determine their opinions on the influence of loyalty programmes on their behaviour. Furthermore, there is a need for quantitative studies on the use of loyalty programmes by hotels in Saudi Arabia to support the conclusions provided by this qualitative research as well as attaining generalisable findings.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Interview Questions

The Question	Objective	Literature Underpinning the Question
Tell me about the current loyalty programmes that you are using and tell me how they have evolved?	To investigate the extent to which hotels in Saudi Arabia use loyalty programs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer loyalty is good for business because they are the main pillars of growth and profits (Ruzeviciute and Kamleitner 2017). • The most important step towards establishing a good business is building customer loyalty (Ranabhat 2018). • It is essential to come up with exciting offers to attract customers and keep the loyal ones vesting your shops (Ranabhat 2018).
How do you measure the effectiveness of the loyalty programme?	To draw a conclusion on the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The success of the loyalty program ought not to entirely be based on monetary matters, but it should reflect many other activities that help to support the loyalty program (Alkhulayfi 2016).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the satisfaction levels of clients can be essential in helping a hotel achieve greater financial success (Jehanzeb et al., 2013).
<p>What information do you use when building your loyalty programme?</p>	<p>To investigate the extent to which hotels in Saudi Arabia use loyalty programs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two major factors should be considered when developing a loyalty program, which are customer behaviors and attitudes (AL-Hazmi 2018). • Customer behaviour examines how the customer has been purchasing a product over a period of time from the same provider (Yi and Jeon 2013). • Customer attitude examines the probability customer has to make repurchase and give recommendations about the products to other potential customers (AL-Hazmi 2018).

<p>How has your hotel benefited from loyalty programmes? What impact do they have on customer attraction and retention?</p>	<p>To investigate whether the use of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia has an impact on attracting new customers. To investigate whether the use of loyalty programmes has helped hotels in Saudi Arabia increase business through customer retention.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer loyalty leads to repeat purchases and leads to expansion and an increase in market share of the business which, when summed up, are key ingredients to higher profitability by the company (Charania 2011).
<p>What type of customer data do you collect through your loyalty programme? What do you do to ensure customers' privacy and confidentiality when managing these data?</p>	<p>To determine how hotels in Saudi Arabia manage the data they collect from customers via loyalty programmes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are five types of customer data that the hotel will collect through loyalty programs, including names, gender, date of birth, email address, and postal or zip address (Al-Saggaf and Islam 2014). • This data is very essential in a building because it will enable the hotels to create targeted messages and position themselves more effectively (Kong and Liang 2012).

Appendix 2: Interview Transcription

Notes	Time	Date	Hotel Name
Mr. Ahmed Mamdouh Executive Sales Manager	20:48	3 June 2019	Hilton Convention Hotel

Interviewer: Thanks for this interview.....Would you like to read the questions before you start?

Participant: No, it's ok, you can start.

Interviewer: Tell me about the current loyalty programmes that you are using?

Participant: (participant's mobile rings): Sorry, we are using Honors...Hilton Honors.

This programme is created by Hilton hotels worldwide. Hilton now has 16 brands all over the world. We now have thousands of hotels around the world. All these hotels are using the current programme, including our hotel. It is considered one of the most popular loyalty programmes and is widespread.

Interviewer: Ok, tell me how it has evolved in Saudi Arabia?

Participant: Umm can you rephrase the question?

Interviewer: What I mean is: since the hotel started using the loyalty programme, how has it developed?

Participant: It has not been developed in Saudi Arabia. But it develops by adding more options inside the programme such as advantages and developed by adding partners in Saudi Arabia and converting points between our programme and their programmes, such as airlines and car rental offices.

Interviewer: How do loyalty programmes affect the hotel industry?

Participant: This is a difficult question (laugh)... Possibly, the Honors Programme has helped in the hotel sector, the presence of loyal customers and dispensed with tourism companies as intermediaries. Also, promotional copies and offers to customers through the programme have helped the success of the hotel marketing plan.

Interviewer: Let us go to the third question. What benefits and methods are used in loyalty programmes?

Participant: The first thing [is] we have a site which is hilton.com. When you want to book in the first hotel you will see to offer the guest membership in the programme because once you log in to take the advantages of the first special in the price of members and the guarantee of the price which is less The price you can find and will show you all your data and the number of points you have and the level if you (Blue or Silver or Gold or Diamond) and based on which you have different advantages such as free nights and free breakfast.

Interviewer: How do you measure the effectiveness of the loyalty programme?

Participant: I want to tell you that 25% of the occupancy rate in the hotel is all members of the Hilton Honors. This is, of course, very effective, and our reports show us revenue through the programme. OK... We have a programme of customer satisfaction scale after check out, as well as classify customers and service, also the goal we have achieved, which we work for our members of our distinguished, of course we measure the effectiveness of the programme by reporting everything for the programme of revenue and customer satisfaction.

Interviewer: What information do you use when building your loyalty programme?

Participant: The information we use? Could you explain more?

Interviewer: What information do you need about the guest when the programme is created by the company?

Participant: We need communication information such as names, addresses for the guests and know the needs of the customer and what services he prefers in the hotel to determine the correct objectives of the programme and market our products.

Interviewer: How has your hotel benefited from loyalty programmes?

Participant: Look... (exhales) Everything that will be in the hotel's interest. Ok... I mean, for example, as I mentioned earlier, 25% of the guests were members of the programme and is a good proportion and achieve us financial profits and customer loyalty to us. In our report to all the hotels, we have 89 million members and, during the

year, 4 million new members joined in, and, in all the hotels of the group worldwide, the proportion of members is 60% of the occupancy rate.

Interviewer: What impact do they have on customer attraction and retention?

Participant: Of course, the hotel has a great impact and effectiveness in retaining and attracting customers, and this is reflected in our report. The programme is also the best because of the possibilities and the presence of hotels everywhere and the rapid spread of the programme in the world. Our team also attracts new customers after explaining the benefits they will receive when registering a membership and encourages the customer to continue using the programme. The client can use the programme from the site or application. The programme like travel management programme because the guest will find hotels, cars, rental and airlines by partners.

Interviewer: What type of customer data do you collect through your loyalty programme? What do you do with this data? How do you manage them?

Participant: We collect communication data for marketing purposes or to communicate with the customer, but the customer must agree to that. Of course, all data is subject to standards of privacy and information security policy.

Interviewer: What do you do to ensure customers' privacy and confidentiality when managing these data?

Participant: There are standards that we commit to in order to ensure the confidentiality of information. We protect the programme through a powerful protection programme that helps in saving data, and also we warn the client to publish or print his data. Data

access is only through the administrator or the person authorised to manage it by Hilton Group. (Talks to another person who interrupted the interview). Sorry for that. We also guarantee the confidentiality of the information by conducting training for the team working on the programme and performing annual and ongoing maintenance to protect the programme and the clients' data.

Interviewer: That's all, thanks for the interview.

Participant: Thank you.

Appendix 3: Participant consent form

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم

Place of interview

مكان المقابلة

Date of interview

تاريخ المقابلة

أوافق على عمل مقابلة شخصية مع الباحث و ذلك لمساعدته في الوصول للبيانات المطلوبة للبحث العلمي عن استخدام و فاعلية برامج الولاء في الفنادق السعودية. يحق للمشارك الاحتفاظ بهويته و عدم الإفصاح عنها عند طلبه. سوف يتم استخدام البيانات في البحث العلمي، من المتوقع أن يتوافق البحث مع سياسة الفندق القياسية والمتطلبات الأخلاقية ذات الصلة.

I agree to a personal interview with the researcher to help him to collect the primary data for research on the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in Saudi hotels. The participant is entitled to remain anonymous upon request. The data will be used in scientific research. The research will be expected to comply with hotel standard policies and relevant ethical requirements.

الإسم

التوقيع

Name

Signature

Please initial or tick box

I agree to take part in this research which is to investigate the use and effectiveness of loyalty programmes in hotels in Saudi Arabia.

The researcher has explained to my satisfaction the purpose, principles and procedures of the study and the possible risks involved.

I have read the information sheet and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved.

I agree to the researcher taking recordings during the project.

I understand how the data collected will be used, and that any confidential information will normally be seen only by the researchers and will not be revealed to anyone else. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without

giving a reason and without incurring consequences from doing so. I agree that data collected may be archived as per University of Brighton processes and it will be sorted for ten years.

Appendix 4: Sample coding of Hotel managers' responses

The approach to coding will go through the processes mentioned below:

Sample coding approach

CODES

